

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXXIX. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with Chelating Azo Dye Ligands, 1-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl-1')azo-1-cyanoethyl Acetate and 1-(2'-Carboxyphenyl-1')azo-1-cyanoethyl Acetate

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Azo dyes are versatile chelating ligands¹. The present communication reports the synthesis of two new bis-bidentate azo dyes (Fig. 1) and their trimeric metal complexes.

R = OH, COOH

Fig. 1

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) support the formation of 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complexes with compositions $[M_3L_2/L_2'Cl_4(H_2O)_6] \cdot [M_3'L_2 / L_2'Cl_4]$, where $M(II) = Co, Ni, Cu, Zn$, $M'(II) = Cd, Hg$; LH = 1-(2'-hydroxyphenyl-1')azo-1-cyanoethyl acetate; L'H = 1-(2'-carboxyphenyl-1')azo-1-cyanoethyl acetate. All the complexes are stable at room temperature. No loss of water molecules takes place when the Co, Ni, Cu and Zn complexes are heated at 130° indicating the coordinated nature of all the water molecules. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from the low Λ_M values (4.2–7.9 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

The ir bands of azo dye ligands at 3 200 (LH) and 3 400 cm^{-1} (L'H) due to ν_{OH} , was lowered due to intramolecular O-H...N hydrogen

bonding. The absence of this band in the metal complexes indicates deprotonation of OH showing its coordination to the metal ions. The band at 1 450 cm^{-1} (LH) due to phenolic C–O vibration shifted to ca 1 430 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes, indicating the bonding of phenolic oxygen atom to the metal ions. The bands at 1 575 (LH) 1 660 cm^{-1} (L'H) can be assigned to –N=N–vibration. A lowering of this band by 150 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates indicates the coordination of both the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal atom². The ligand band at 1 675 (LH) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (L'H) assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$, showed negative shift in the spectra of the metal complexes, indicating the bonding of esteric carbonyl oxygen atoms to the metal ions³. In the spectrum of the ligand (L'H), $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ appeared at 1 730 and 1 460 cm^{-1} respectively. In the metal chelates, these bands appeared at 1 620–1 630 and 1 405–1 415 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = \sim 215 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), indicating the presence of monodentate carboxylate group⁴. The band at 2 200 (LH) and 2 210 cm^{-1} (L'H) due to $\nu_{C\equiv N}$ remained unaltered in the chelates indicating its noncoordination to the metal ions⁵. In the spectra of the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, the presence of coordinated water molecules is indicated by the appearance of broad bands as well as double humps at 3 150–3 550 cm^{-1} followed by a sharp peak at 840–845 cm^{-1} assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively⁶. In

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis(%) : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.
	M	C	H	N	Cl	
LH	—	55.5	4.3	17.8	—	—
(Black)		(56.0)	4.7	(18.1)		
L'H	—	54.7	4.1	15.9	—	—
(Blue)		(55.3)	4.2	(16.1)		
[Co ₃ L ₂ Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	19.2	28.9	3.2	9.1	15.4	5.1
(Black)	(19.8)	29.6	3.5	9.4	(15.9)	
[Co ₃ L ₂ 'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	18.3	29.9	3.1	8.5	14.5	5.0
(Green)	(18.6)	30.4	3.3	8.8	(14.9)	
[Ni ₃ L ₂ Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	19.3	29.2	3.4	9.1	15.4	3.1
(Blue)	(19.7)	29.6	3.5	9.4	(15.9)	
[Ni ₃ L ₂ 'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	18.3	29.8	3.1	8.2	14.4	3.2
(Green)	(18.6)	30.4	3.3	8.8	(14.9)	
[Cu ₃ L ₂ Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	20.7	28.7	3.2	8.8	15.2	1.8
(Blue)	(21.0)	29.1	3.5	9.2	(15.6)	
[Cu ₃ L ₂ 'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	19.4	29.5	3.1	8.2	14.4	1.82
(Red)	(19.7)	29.9	3.3	8.7	(14.7)	
[ZnL ₂ Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	21.1	28.6	3.2	8.7	15.2	—
(Blue)	(21.5)	29.0	3.5	9.2	(15.5)	
[Zn ₃ L ₂ 'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₆]	20.2	29.2	3.1	8.2	14.2	
(Light yellow)	(20.3)	29.8	3.3	8.6	(14.6)	
[Cd ₃ L ₂ Cl ₄]	34.8	27.3	1.9	8.4	17.6	
(Light pink)	(35.7)	27.9	2.1	8.9	(15.0)	
[Cd ₃ L ₂ 'Cl ₄]	30.2	25.6	1.6	7.2	12.2	
(Orange)	(30.4)	26.0	1.8	7.5	(12.8)	
[Hg ₃ L ₂ Cl ₄]	49.2	21.4	1.5	6.7	11.5	
(Brown)	(49.8)	21.8	1.6	6.9	(11.7)	
[Hg ₃ L ₂ 'Cl ₄]	43.5	20.4	1.2	5.5	9.8	
(Orange)	(43.8)	20.9	1.4	6.1	(10.3)	

*LH = 1-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl-1')-azo-1-cyanoethyl acetate; L'H=1-(2'-carboxyphenyl-1')-azo-1-cyanoethyl acetate.

the far-ir spectra of the metal chelates, the bands at 220–250, 320 and 400 cm^{-1} , assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations respectively⁷.

The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibited normal magnetic moments expected for high-spin octahedral complexes⁸.

The electronic spectra of the two cobalt complexes showed four bands at 8 570, 17 225, 19 920 and 31 565 cm^{-1} . The first three bands can be assigned respectively to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions in conformity with an octahedral configuration and a CT band⁹. In case of the nickel complexes the bands at 10 885, 17 350, 23 820 and 31 540 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(P)$ transitions, and CT band¹⁰.

The results suggest an octahedral geometry for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. In case of the Cu^{II} complexes, one broad band at 13 320–15 480 cm^{-1} with the maxima at 14 450 cm^{-1} has been assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition, indicating the existence of a distorted-octahedral stereochemistry around the Cu^{II} ions¹¹.

From the room temperature esr spectrum of the complexes [Cu₂L₂Cl₄(H₂O)₆] at X-band, g values ($g_{\text{I}} = 2.0524$, $g_{\text{II}} = 2.2550$) have been calculated using Kneubuhl's method¹². It is evident from the shape of spectrum that the symmetry around Cu^{II} ion in the unit cell is tetragonal (elongated octahedral) with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state. The Q band esr spectrum of [Cu₃L₂'Cl₄(H₂O)₆] indicates a rhombic $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state symmetry with three g

NOTE

values, being $g_1 = 2.0284$, $g_2 = 2.0804$ and $g_3 = 2.2082$. The axial symmetry parameter (G) of the two complexes are found to be 4.86 and 3.827 respectively, indicating the g values being nearer to the molecular g values with magnetically equivalent ions in the unit cell. The g values of both the complexes are less than 2.3 which shows that the complexes are largely covalent¹³. Further, these values are consistent with the mixed Cu-N and Cu-O bonded complexes.

The Zn^{II} complexes can be suggested to have octahedral stereochemistry and the Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes the tetrahedral configuration, based on analytical, thermal and IR spectral data.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B D H or E Merck make. The ligands were prepared by the coupling reaction of diazonium chloride solutions obtained from *o*-aminophenol and *o*-aminobenzoic acid with alkaline solution of ethyl cyanoacetate.

The metal complexes were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of the ligands separately with the metal chlorides in 1:1 molar ratio ~1 h. After cooling, the pH of the solution was raised to 7 and the resulting complexes were washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

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